

THE IMPORTANCE OF READING ACTIVITIES IN READING COMPREHENSION

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Annotation: Present work can be used as a practical depot for taking data about the importance of reading, its types and methods of creating activities on reading classes. On the other hand, specific aspects which are used to develop reading strategies in general schools were noted. Teaching and learning reading skill demand to practice many times. In order to be interesting this process the teachers should use different kinds of reading handouts. Our course work includes examples of handouts that can be utilized in reading lessons.

Key words: *educational contexts, pre-reading activities, sampling error, rhetorical structure, Interactive model, graphophonic, syntactic, top-down strategies.*

Reading in English is an important part of language learning because it helps you develop other related skills like grammar, vocabulary, and writing. Reading allows language learners to explore topics that they love and stories that engage them. Reading, even at a slow pace exposes students to more sentences, grammar, and new vocabulary per minute than the average, short class, TV show, or song. This is why students who read foreign books are able to speak more fluently than students who don't, despite having done the same amount of classes. Reading is a communication process requiring a series of skills, such as reading is a thinking process rather than an exercise in eye movements. Based on the definition above, that reader's knowledge of the world depends on lived experience. This is different in different countries, regions and cultures. H. Douglas Brown said that reading is likewise a skill that teachers simply expect learners to acquire. Reading arguably the most essential skill for success in all educational contexts[1]. According to J. Charles reading is both process and product, the process of reading involves the interaction between the reader and the text-how the reader is deciphering the writing on the page, what he or she is thinking about while reading and reader is monitoring his or her reading.

A reader reads a text to understand its meaning, as well as to put that understanding to use. A person reads a text to learn, to find out information, to be entertained, to reflect or as religious practice. The purpose of reading is closely connected to person's motivation to read. It will also affect the way a book is read. We read a dictionary in a different way from the way we read a novel. In the classroom, teachers need to be aware of their students' learning needs.

Studies of pre-reading activities for native speakers have demonstrated the facilitative effects of activating reader's prior knowledge relevant to understanding of the new text. Not only do pre-reading activities prepare native speakers for the concepts that follow, but making the reading task easier and connecting the new concept more meaningfully to prior knowledge, pre-reading activities make reading a more enjoyable task. Pre-reading activities are thus intended to activate appropriate knowledge structures or provide knowledge that the reader lacks. The present study intends to investigate the effects of pre-reading activities on comprehension of engineering students[2]. It is hypothesized that employing the pre-reading activities would significantly improve student's ability in comprehension. For the realization of this objective two groups of participants were employed and put in the two experimental and control groups. The comparison of mean scores made by subjects of the two groups provided evidence to the effect that whether the difference between teaching strategies, if any, were due to experimental treatment or sampling error.

Most scholars would agree that reading is one of the most important skills for educational and professional success. In highlighting the importance of reading comprehension Rivers stated that "reading is the most important activity in any language class, not only as a source of information and a pleasurable activity, but also as a means of consolidating and extending one's which are knowledge of the language". Reading reinforces the learner's other language skills. Krashen confirms that those who read more, have larger vocabularies, do better on test of grammar and write better Chastian while accepting the significance of reading for meaning claimed that all reading activities serve to facilitate communication fluency in each of the other language skills. According to Eskey, in advanced levels of second language the ability to read the written language at a reasonable rate and with good comprehension has long been recognized to be as oral skills if not more important.

A significant body of literature posits that reading is an interactive process According to Grabbe the notion of reading as an interactive process refers to "a kind of dialogue between the reader and the text". The notion of reading as an interactive process evolved from the schema theory and is often termed top-down approach to reading[3]. Carrell distinguishes between formal schemata the reader's knowledge of formal, rhetorical structure of the texts and content schemata – previous knowledge which the reader posses. In an interactive model, the reader is not seen to progress in just one direction (bottom-up or top-down) in understanding the text, but as being able to alternate approaches as necessary (Barnett, 1989). The reader is seen as able to draw simultaneously from a variety of sources to understand the text such as lexical, orthographic, schematic, semantic, syntactical, and visual. Thus reading is seen as a

simultaneous perceptual and cognitive process. Interactive model of reading comprehension not only acknowledges the role of background knowledge, but also it stresses the significance of processing actual words of the texts. Goodman maintains that, “ ... the goal of reading is constructing meaning in response to text. It requires interactive use of graphophonic, syntactic, and semantic cues to construct meaning.” Although he is often referred to as a leading advocate of the top –down approach, his model by his own admission is interactive.

An interactive model of reading posited by Grabbe usually refers to interplay of both bottom-up and top-down reading strategies. Bottom-up strategies include decoding graphic features and grammatical characteristics, while top-down strategies include predicting, applying background knowledge and recognizing global text structure. The notion of top-down strategies is usually used in the literature to include both global strategies for processing the text as well as activating conceptual knowledge of the world. According to Dubin and Bycina, the interactive modal entails the reading processes to be as such that the visual data are transmitted to brain where they are matched with existing knowledge. Then on the basis of this experience, predictions are made about the content of the text, upon which, further sampling of the data are either confirmed or revised.

The goals of Pre-reading stage are to activate the student’s knowledge of the subject, to provide any language preparation that might be needed for coping with the passage and, finally to motivate the learners to want to read the text. Tudor call pre-reading activities “enabling activities” because they provide a reader with the necessary background to organize activity and to comprehend the material (these experiences involve understanding the purpose (S) for reading and building a knowledge base necessary for dealing with the content and the structure of the material). They say that pre-reading activities elicit prior knowledge, and focus attention. Various techniques have been suggested by some authors to mobilize existing knowledge including the use of pictures, movies and even role – plays[4]. Research has not determined which of these is the most effective. So teachers are free to experiment according to the nature of reading material and inclinations of their classes. In an academic setting, however, more formal techniques might be appropriate, of course different scholars listed different types of pre-reading activities, suggests, Word Association, Discussion and Text Surveys.

In conclusion pre reading, while reading and post reading activities play an important role for reading comprehension so students are stimulated by these activities and these activities increase the students’ skills and strategies and abilities for reading comprehension. In conclusion; the study indicates that if practical and effective reading activities are applied in

reading classes students can create, relate, organize and realize meaning in written text. Reading can be defined constructing meaning in text. Readers can construct meaning and evaluate text through the author's opinions. In these three stages (pre, while and post reading) students become active, efficient, effective, and independent readers. Based on this discussion; reading activities play an important role for reading comprehension and deeper level of understanding can be achieved by means of these reading activities and students read and understand the text easily. As we stated before, teachers should teach to students how to think how to use strategies and techniques in reading process so students can identify their needs and goals in reading classroom. We can state that students can use cognitive skills in reading activities. In this research we focus on functions of reading activities and students are activated by series of reading activities by the researcher.

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